

ISic2932

I.Sicily inscription 2932

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331425

1. ἐπι (νεμήσεως) α' ²⁷ἐπι(νεμήσεως) ια'²⁷.
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645316

PHI 331425

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0872

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1987.0553

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*.

28-29: 3-29. At 15 no.44

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio*.

Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 587 n.130

Ferrua, A 1946-1947. Florilegio d'iscrizioni paleocristiane di Sicilia. *Rendiconti della Pontifica accademia romana di archeologia*. 22: 227-239. At 238 no.48

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2932. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387753>